

Citation for the Presentation of the 2015

ICPE Medal to

Professor Kaihua Zhao

China

at the World Conference on Physics

Education, São Paulo, Brazil

July 2016

Professor Kaihua Zhao is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2015 in recognition of his sustained efforts in physics education over more than a half century, both domestically and internationally.

Kaihua Zhao graduated from Beijing University in 1950 and received a doctorate from Moscow State University in 1958. Dr. Zhao immediately became a faculty member of Beijing University, becoming Professor in 1978. From 1983 to 1990 he was the Dean of the Department of Physics and was the Vice Chair of the Chinese Physical Society from 1991 to 1999.

For more than 50 years Professor Zhao has taught tens of thousands of students. He has compiled and composed 23 textbooks on various physics topics. These textbooks have played fundamental roles in physics education in the Chinese Universities and become key reference books for teachers and students in a vast number of schools. Especially he has actively promoted the integration of scientific research achievements into teaching and learning. His textbooks have won the highest level National Textbook Award three times and twice the prize of the State Education Commission.

In 1984 China started to join the International Physics Olympiad (IPhO). Professor Zhao was one of the early organizers of Chinese teams. In 1994, he presided the 25th IPhO held in Beijing, which enhanced greatly the international influence on physics education in China.

Professor Zhao was the pioneering person to introduce the physics teaching in China to the international community. Also, he made many efforts to organize international conferences on physics education, such as the US-China-Japan International Conference on Physics Teaching.

Today the International Commission on Physics Education takes great pleasure in recognizing Professor Zhao's devotion to Physics Education and uncountable number of students and teachers.

Hideo Nitta

Chairman of ICPE